

A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW ON *KUPEELU* (*Strychnos nux-vomica* Linn.) W.S.R TO ITS THERAPEUTIC UTILITY

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ABSTRACT

Kupeelu is botanically identified as *Strychnosnux-vomica* Linn. and it is considered one among the *Upavisha Varga*. It is well known by its many synonyms like *Vishamushti*, *Kaakatinduka*, *Kulaka*, *Kuchila*, *Vishatinduka*, etc. There are many references regarding the drug *Kupeelu* in classical texts that are mentioned according to the time. Ayurveda strictly recommend the use of this drug in therapeutics only after proper *Shodhana* (purificatory procedure). Use of impure *Kupeelu* can lead to the manifestations of poisonous signs and symptoms, such as convulsions, twitching of muscles of face, cyanosis, dilated pupils, frothy salivation, epigastric pain and death is incredibly painful. The same purified *Kupeelu* seeds are used for the treatment of Asthma, obesity, intestinal worm infestation, infertility, hemorrhoids, diarrhea, intoxication etc. This article is a compilation in detail about various aspects of *Kupeelu* mainly focusing on the purificatory methods and the therapeutic utility mentioned in different Ayurveda texts.

Key Words-*Kupeelu, Shodhana, Strychnos nus-vomica* Linn., *Upavisha, Vishamushti*

INTRODUCTION

Kupeelu (*Strychnos nuxvomica* Linn.) is a spinal poison of vegetable origin, considered under *Upavisha*.^{1,2,3} According to Ayurveda any potent poison can be utilized in treatment as an excellent medicine if used judiciously, on the contrary a potent medicine that can act as a potent poison if used unjudiciously⁴. One of the best example for such use of potent poison in treatment is *Kupeelu*, if used properly. As later authors considered it under the *Upavisha* group of drugs it is to be used for therapeutic purpose only after subjecting to specific purification processes known as *Shodhana*⁵.

The categorization of some drugs, such as *Upavisha*, is to make the physician, cautious about the unexpected ill effects of such drugs. Unexpected adverse reactions can occur due to accidental use of a poisonous herb/medicine by the patient, miss identification of herbs so that a toxic herb is mistaken as harmless variety, improper purification of the poisonous ingredients, overdose, irrational prescription, and self-medication⁶.

Kupeelu seeds contains various alkaloids such as Strychnine, Brucine, Vomocine, Kajine, Novocain (N-methyl pseudobrucine), Isostrychnine, Cuchiloside, Loganic acid etc. Strychnine and Brucine are the two main toxic alkaloids responsible for the manifestation of convulsions.⁷ Use of impure *Kupeelu* can lead to the manifestations of poisonous signs and symptoms, such as convulsions, twitching of muscles of face, cyanosis, dilated pupils, frothy salivation, epigastric pain and death is incredibly painful⁸.

The chances of accidental poisoning are also more due to the attractiveness of the fruit and the wide distribution of the plant. The seeds of *Kupeelu* are widely used as rodenticide and it can be taken as a medium for suicide also.

In classical textbooks of Ayurveda, actions of *Kupeelu* are explained as *Shothahara*, *Vedanasthapana*, *Uttejaka*, *Nadibalya*, *Deepana*, *Paachana*, *Jwaraghna*, *Arshoghna*, *Graahi*, *Shoolaprashamana*, *Hridayottejaka*, *Kaphaghna*, *Kasahara*, *Vajikarana*, *Balya*, *Kushtaghna*, *Kandughna*, *Swedaapanayana* etc., and therapeutically also it is used in the management of *Alarka Visha*, *Vrana*, *Mushika Visha*⁹, in *Vatavikaras* like *Ardita*, *Kampa*, *Baadhirya*, *Shayyamutra*, *Napumsakata*¹⁰ etc. There are more than 60 formulations containing *Kupeelu* like *Navajeevana Rasa*¹¹, *Agnitundi Rasa*¹², *Laxmivilasa Rasa*¹³, *Vishagarbha Taila*¹⁴ etc. which

are used successfully in day-to-day practice by Ayurveda physicians in the treatment of many diseases.

DRUG REVIEW

Kupeelu is botanically identified as *Strychnosnux-vomica* Linn. and it is considered one among the *Upavisha Varga*. It is an evergreen glabrous tree and is distributed throughout India. The synonyms of the drugs are *Vishamushti*, *Kaakatinduka*, *Kulaka*, *Kuchila*, *Vishatinduka*, etc.

In the classical textbooks of Ayurveda, written in different periods there are various references regarding drug *Kupeelu*.

Samgraha Kaala:

Sharangadhara Samhita¹⁵:

Vishamushti is mentioned as one of the ingredients in the formulation *Agnitundi Rasa*.

Table 1:classification of *Kupeelu* in different *Nighantus*:

Sl. No.	Nighantu	Varga
1.	Dhanwantari Nighantu	<i>Amradi Varga¹⁶</i>
2.	Kaiyadeva Nighantu	<i>Oushadi Varga¹⁷</i>
3.	Raja Nighantu	<i>Prabhadradi Varga¹⁸</i>
4.	Madanapaala Nighantu	<i>Phaladi Varga¹⁹</i>
5.	Bhavapraksha Nighantu	<i>Amradiphala Varga²⁰</i>
6.	Nighantu Adarsha	<i>Vishatidukadi Varga²¹</i>
7.	Priya Nighantu	<i>Shatapushpadi Varga²²</i>
8.	Shodala Nighantu	<i>Karaveeradi Varga²³</i>

9.	Shaligrama Nighnatu	<i>Phala Varga</i> ²⁴
10.	Dravyaguna Hastaamalaka	<i>Kupeelu Kula</i> ²⁵

Table 2 : Synonyms of *Kupeelu* according to different authors

Sl.no	Synonyms	K.N ¹⁷	R.N ¹⁸	M.N ¹⁹	Bp.N ²⁰	N.A ²¹	P.N ²²	R.T ²⁶
1.	<i>Kuchilaa</i>							+
2.	<i>Kuchela</i>							+
3.	<i>Vishatindu</i>		+					+
4.	<i>Kuchelaka</i>							+
5.	<i>Vishatinduka</i>			+	+	+		
6.	<i>Kaaraskara</i>		+				+	+
7.	<i>Ramyaphala</i>		+					+
8.	<i>Kupaaka</i>		+					+
9.	<i>Vishamushtika</i>							+
10.	<i>Vishamushti</i>	+						+
11.	<i>Kshudramusti</i>	+						
12.	<i>Keshamusti</i>	+						
13.	<i>Sumustika</i>	+						
14.	<i>Kaalakoota</i>		+					+
15.	<i>Vishadruma</i>		+					
16.	<i>Garadruma</i>		+					

17.	<i>Kulaka</i>				+			
18.	<i>Kaakatinduka</i>				+	+		
19.	<i>Kaakapeeluka</i>			+	+			
20.	<i>Kupeelu</i>			+	+	+		
21.	<i>Kaakendu</i>				+			
22.	<i>Kimpaaka</i>		+					

(K.N: KaiyyadevaNighantu, R.N: Raja Nighantu, M.N: Madanapaala Nighantu, Bp.N: Bhavaprakasha Nighantu, N.A: Nighantu Adarsha, P.N: Priya Nighantu, R.T: Rasa Tarangini)

Rasa- Panchaka

The local or systemic actions of the drugs depend on its *Rasa Panchakas* like *Rasa, Guna, Veerya, Vipaka* and *Prabhava*. Each drugs will act either by their *Rasa, Guna, Veerya, Vipaka* or *Prabhava*. It depends on the individual drugs.

Table 3 : *Rasa-Panchaka* of *Kupeelu* in various *Nighantus*:

Sl.no	Nighantus	<i>Rasa</i>	<i>Guna</i>	<i>Veerya</i>	<i>Vipaka</i>
1.	Kaiyyadeva Nighantu ¹⁷	<i>Katu, Tikta, Kashaya</i>		<i>Ushna</i>	
2.	Raja Nighantu ¹⁸	<i>Katu, Tikta</i>		<i>Ushna</i>	
3.	Madanapaala Nighantu ¹⁹			<i>Sheeta</i>	
4.	Bhavaprakasha Nighantu ²⁰	<i>Tikta</i>	<i>Laghu</i>	<i>Sheeta</i>	
5.	NighantuAdarsha ²¹	<i>Katu</i>		<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Katu</i>

6.	Priya Nighantu ²²	<i>Katu, Tikta</i>	<i>Sara</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	
7.	Shodala Nighantu ²³	<i>Tikta(Mahatikta)</i>			
8.	Rasa Tarangini ²⁷	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Teekshna</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	
9.	Dravyaguna Hastaamalaka ²⁸	<i>Tikta, Katu</i>	<i>Teekshna, Laghu, Ruksha</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Katu</i>

Table 4: Dosha Karma of Kupeelu according to different authors:

<i>Dosha Karma</i>	K.N¹⁷	R.N¹⁸	Bp.N²⁰	N.A²¹	P.N²²	Sho.N²³	Sa.N²⁴	DG.H²⁵
<i>Vatahara</i>		+			+		+	
<i>Vatalam</i>			+					
<i>Pittahara</i>	+							
<i>Kaphahara</i>	+							
<i>Kapha- Asrunashanam</i>		+						
<i>Kapha-Vata- Asrunashanam</i>							+	
<i>Kapha-Pitta Asrunashanam</i>			+					
<i>Kapha-</i>				+		+		+

<i>Vatahara</i>								
<i>Pitta Krit</i>	+							
	(Phala)							

(K.N: KaiyyadevaNighantu, R.N: Raja Nighantu, Bp.N: Bhavaprakasha Nighantu,

N.A: Nighantu Adarsha, P.N: Priya Nighantu, Sho. N: Shoadala Nighantu, Sa.N: Saligrama Nighantu, DG.H: Dravyaguna Hastaamalaka)

Table 5:Shamana Karma of Kupeelu according to different authors:

Sl.No	Shamana Karma	K.N ¹⁷	R.N ¹⁸	M.N ¹⁹	B.P ²⁰	P.N ²²	DG.H ²⁵
1.	<i>Vajeekara</i>					+	
2.	<i>Graahi</i>	+		+	+		
3.	<i>Balya</i>					+	
4.	<i>Madakaari</i>				+		
5.	<i>Paachana</i>					+	+
6.	<i>Deepana</i>					+	+
7.	<i>Vedanasthapana</i>				+		+
8.	<i>Nadi Balakara</i>						+
9.	<i>Shoolahara</i>						+
10.	<i>Hridya</i>						+
11.	<i>Swedahara</i>						+
12.	<i>Kamottejaka</i>						+

13.	<i>Vranahara</i>		+				
14.	<i>Kanduhara</i>		+				
15.	<i>Jantuhara</i>	+					
16.	<i>Krimihara</i>	+					
17.	<i>Medohara</i>	+					

(K.N: KaiyyadevaNighantu, R.N: Raja Nighantu, M.N: Madanpala Nighantu, Bp.N: Bhavaprakasha Nighantu, P.N: Priya Nighantu, DG.H: Dravyaguna Hastamalaka)

Table 6: Rogagnata of Kupeelu according to different authors:

Sl.no	Rogagnata	K.N ¹⁷	R.N ¹⁸	N.A ²¹	Sho.N ²³	Sha.N ²⁴	DG.H ²⁵
1.	<i>Visha</i>				+	+	+
2.	<i>Vrana</i>		+			+	
3.	<i>Kusta</i>	+	+			+	+
4.	<i>Arsha</i>	+	+				
5.	<i>Karshya</i>					+	
6.	<i>Prameha</i>	+					
7.	<i>Visuchika</i>			+			
8.	<i>Shwasa</i>	+					+
9.	<i>Gulma</i>	+					
10.	<i>MushikaVisha</i>	+					
11.	<i>Ardita</i>			+			+

12.	<i>Kampa</i>			+			
13.	<i>Nadishoola</i>			+			
14.	<i>Bhadirya</i>			+			
15.	<i>Shayyamutra</i>			+			+
16.	<i>Napumsakata</i>			+			
17.	<i>Ajeerna</i>			+			
18.	<i>Agnimandhya</i>			+			+

(K.N: Kaiyyadeva Nighantu, R.N: Raja Nighantu, N.A: Nighantu Adarsha, Sho. N: Shoadala Nighantu, Sa.N: Saligrama Nighantu, DG.H: Dravyaguna Hastaamalaka)

VishishtaYoga:

There are many formulations that contains *Kupeelu* as one of the ingredients.

Table 7: *Vishishta Yogas* according to Bhaishajya Ratnavali

Sl.No	<i>VishishtaYogas</i>	Indications
1.	<i>Vishatindukadi Lepa</i> ²⁹	<i>Upadamsha</i>
2.	<i>Kupeelubeejadi Kwatha</i> ³⁰	<i>Lasika Meha, Ojo Meha, Manjista Meha</i>
3.	<i>Vishatinduka Taila</i> ³¹	<i>Vata Rakta, Kusta, Vaivarnya, Twakdosha</i>
4.	<i>Vicharchikari Taila</i> ³²	<i>Vicharchika, Naadivrana, Upadamsha, Bhagandhara</i>

Table 8: Vishishta Yogas according to Yoga Ratnakara:

Sl.no	VishishtaYogas	Indications
1.	<i>Vishagarbha Taila</i> ³³	<i>Pakshaghata, Hanustamba, Manyastamba, Katigraha, SarvangaGraham,</i>
2.	<i>Mahavishagarbha Taila</i> ³⁴	<i>Sarva Vata Vyadi, Gradhrasi, Sarvanga Graham, Dandapatanaka, Karnanaada</i>
3.	<i>VardhamaanaKaraskara Phala Prayoga</i> ³⁵	<i>Alarka Visha</i>

Table 9: VishishtaYogas according to RasaTarangini:

Sl.no	VishishtaYoga	Indications
1.	<i>Navajeevana Rasa</i> ³⁶	<i>Agnimandya, NaadiBalya, AntraShoolaHara</i>
2.	<i>Agnitundi Rasa</i> ³⁷	<i>Deepana, Paachana, Agni Mandhya, Naadibalya, Kativedana, Atisaara</i>
3.	<i>LaxmivilasaRasa</i> ³⁸	<i>Deha Pustakara, Veerya Vriddhikara, Agnimandhya</i>
4.	<i>Shoolanirmoolana Rasa</i> ³⁹	<i>Agnimandhya, Gulma, Ghrahani, Shoolavikara</i>
5.	<i>Suptivataari Rasa</i> ⁴⁰	<i>Supti Vata</i>
6.	<i>Saarameya Vishapaho Yoga</i> ⁴¹	<i>Kukkura Visha</i>
7.	<i>Vishatinduka Taila</i> ⁴²	<i>Pakshaghata (For external application)</i>

Table 10. *Vishishta Yogas* according to Rasendra Sara Sangraha:

Sl.no	Name of the Yoga	Therapeutic uses
1.	<i>Agnimukha Rasa</i> ⁴³	<i>Shoola, Agnimandhya</i>
2.	<i>Shoolahara Yoga</i> ⁴⁴	<i>Gulma, Shoola, Grahani, Atisaara, Ajeerna, Agnimandhya</i>
3.	<i>Sarvangasundara Rasa</i> ⁴⁵	<i>Vata Vikara, Sarva Shoola</i>
4.	<i>Galitakushtari Rasa</i> ⁴⁶	<i>Kushta</i>

Table 11. *Vishishta Yogas* according to other texts:

Author/ Book	<i>Vishista Yoga</i>	Indication
Sahasra Yoga ⁴⁷	<i>Karaskara Ghrita</i>	<i>Sandivata, Amavata, Vatavikaras</i>
Rasa Prakasha Sudhakara ⁴⁸	<i>Krimivirechanavati</i>	<i>Krimi</i>
Bharata Bhaishajya Ratnakara ⁴⁹	<i>Sameera Gajakesari Rasa</i>	<i>Vata Vikara, Kubjata, Gridrasi, Kampa</i>
Sharangadhara ⁵⁰	<i>Agnitundivati rasa</i>	<i>Agnimandhya, Sarva Roga Nashaka</i>

Shodhana:

Shodhana plays a very important role in Ayurveda system of medicine, as it reduces *Visha* or toxic substances from the drug and adds some special qualities to the drug. *Kupeelu* or any *Upa Vishag* group of drugs can be used in the treatment very effectively only after subjecting it to some specific purification processes known as '*Shodhana*'. There are various procedures mentioned for *Shodhana* of *Kupeelu*.

Following are the different *Shodhana* procedures according to the different classics:

1. *Kupeelu* seeds are kept in an earthen pot containing *Kaanji* for three days, after three days the seeds are taken out, the pericarp must be removed. Then the seeds are dried in sun light and pounded to prepare powder.⁵¹
2. *Kupeelu* seeds are fried in a pan by adding *Go Ghrita* on *Mandaagni* till the seeds became *Kapisha Varna*. The outer layer is removed, seeds grounded to prepare powder.⁵²
3. A *Potali* containing *Kupeelu* seeds is to be suspended in *Dola Yantra* containing milk. This is to be heated on *Mandagni* for three hours. Then the seeds can be taken out and washed in hot water. Afterwards the seeds are dried and are grounded to prepare powder.⁵³
4. *Kupeelu* seeds are immersed in an earthen pot containing mixture of *Gomutra* and *Gomaya* for 3 days. On the 4th day seeds can be taken out and the outer layer of seeds and *Ankuras* are removed. Then seeds are washed and dried in shade.⁵⁴
5. The *Kupeelu* seeds are boiled in *Go Dugdha*. Seeds are taken out and the outer layer of seeds and *Ankura* are removed. Then washed and dry in shade.⁵⁵

Maatra⁵⁶:*ShodhitaKupeeluBeejaChoorna* dose is one fourth to one *Ratti*.

Pratyoushadhas⁵⁷:

Different antidotes have been mentioned for *Kupeelu* poisoning in *Kriya Koumudi* textbook of Kerala namely:

- 1) *Lavanga Swarasa*.
- 2) *Madhu* and *Ghritha* with *Sharkara*.
- 3) Tender leaves of *Gunja* for internal and external use.
- 4) *Tugaaksheeri* with *Sharkara*.
- 5) *Jambu PatraSwarasa*.
- 6) *Kashaya* of *Nagara*, *Maricha* and *Shilajatu*.
- 7) *Kapittha Swarasa*.
- 8) *Kalka* of tender leaves of *Chitraka* with *Navaneeta*.
- 9) Powdered *Bhringaraaja* and powder of *Tila*
- 10) *Kalka* prepared out of stem bark of *Jambu* with milk for both internal and external administration.
- 11) *Palaasha Twak*

DISCUSSION

Kupeelu, commonly known as *nux vomica* is widely used in Ayurveda formulations, even though it is identified as a poisonous plant. It is categorized under *Upavisha Varga*; the group of drugs having less toxicity and are less fatal but can produce certain toxic symptoms if administered. Hence, before the usage it is very much essential to have the proper purificatory procedures done for this drug. Various media like cow's urine, cow's milk, cow's ghee, *Kanji* are commonly used for the *Shodhana*. Some traditional practitioners use castor oil and ginger juice also. In ancient period it was not used much as a medicine, but chiefly employed to poison dogs, cats, crows etc.

Review of literature indicates that *Brihat Trayees* did not mention *Vishatinduka* or *Kupeelu*. Shodala denoted it as *Visa Tinduka* while Bhavamishra described it as *Kakatinduka* or *Kupeelu*. As the reference of *Kupeelu* is there in Sharangadhara Samhita as an ingredient of the formulation *Agnitundi Rasa*, it can be inferred that the use of *Kupeelu* has started from *Sangraha Kaala* onwards. After this period the details of *Kupeelu* have been found in various *Nighantus* and it has been considered as *Upavisha* by various Rasashastra authors. Especially the poisonous side of *Kupeelu* has been highlighted in the textbooks of Rasa Shastra. It is being given importance as a medicinal drug as well, hence for the therapeutic use, the *Shodhana* procedures are mentioned before use. It is mainly indicated as a medicine in *Kandu*, *Kushta*, *Vata Roga*, *Vrana*, *Arshas*, *Jwara*, *Agnimandya* etc. *Kriya Koumudi* is a book which is successfully being followed by the traditional *Visha Vaidyasin* Kerala and in this text, several antidotes have been mentioned for the treatment of *Kupeelu* poisoning.

CONCLUSION

Ayurveda uses mainly herbal source as the medicine and there are many plants which are known to be poisonous also, yet used in practice, after purification. It is stated that even poison becomes nectar after logical administration *Kupeelu* is one among such plant and its seeds are used in various formulations mentioned in Ayurveda classical textbooks. *Upavisha Varga Dravyas* like *Kupeelu* with its vital Phyto-chemical constituents, are utilized in the formulations after proper purification to treat various disorders. It is also very much essential to look into the safety parameters of such drugs and a greater number of phyto-chemical and analytical studies including clinical trials are required for the proper standardization of *Kupeelu*.

REFERENCES

1. Pandit.Kashinath Shastri; Rasa Tarangini 24/163,164;Motilal Banarasidas; Varanasi; 12th edition; 2012; p-676;pp-772
2. Acharya Vaghat; Rasaratnasamuchhaya 10/84; Prof. Siddinandanmishra; Choukambaorientalia; Varanasi;1st edition;2011;p-248;pp-697
3. Dr.Siddhinandanmishra; Rasendrachudamani 9/13; Chaukhambaorientalia; Varanasi; 2ndedition;1999;P-130;pp-332
4. Agnivesh; Charaka;Charakasamhita Su.1/126; VaidyaYaadavji Trikamji Achaarya; Chaukambapublishan Varanasi;reprint 2013;p-23;pp-738
5. Pandit Kashinath Shastri; Rasa Tarangini 24/172-177; Motilal Banarasidas; Varanasi; 12th edition; 2012; p-678;pp-772
6. Ashok Kumar Panda,Saroj Kumar Debnath; Overdose effect of aconite containg Ayurvedic medicine; International Journal of Ayurveda research;Sikkim; vol 1; 2010;p-183
7. Dr. J.L.N. Shastry; Dravyaguna Vijnana; Chaukamba orientalia;Varanasi;vol 2; 2ndedition; 2005;p-353;pp-1134
8. Dr.C. K. Parikh; Parikh's text of Medical jurisprudence and Toxicology; CBC publishers and distributors; Delhi; 6thedition; 1999;p-11.36
9. Dr.Gyanendra Pandey; Dravyaguna Vijnana; Krishnadas academy; Varanasi; vol2; 1stedition;p-336;pp-824
10. Bhavamishra; Bhavaprakash; edited by Brahmashankara Mishra; Choukamba Sanskrita Samsathana; Varanasi; Vol1/19;edition 8th ;p-568;pp-959
11. Kashinathshastri; Rasa tarangini 24/204-209;Motilalbanarasidas;Varanasi;1stedtion;1994;p-684;pp-772
12. Kashinathshastri; Rasa tarangini 24/210-215;Motilalbanarasi das;Varanasi;1stedtion;1994;p-685;pp-772
13. Kashinathshastri; Rasa tarangini 24/216-221; Motilalbanarasi das; Varanasi; 1stedtion; 1994; p-686; pp-772
14. Vaidya Laksmipathishastri; Yogaratnakara Poorvaardha/Vaatavyadhinidaana; Choukhamba Sanskritasamsthana;Varanasi;7th edition;2002; P-531;pp-574

15. Pandit Parashurama;Sharangadhara samhita 12/222,223;Choukambaorientalia;Varanasi; 7th edition2008;p-279;pp-398
16. Prof. Priyavrat Sharma; Dhanvantari Nighantu Amradivarga/34—36; Choukambaorientalia Varanasi;p-154;pp-358
17. .Prof. Priyavrat Sharma; Kaideva Nighantu Oushadivarga/152/600-602; Choukamba orientalia; Varanasi;2009;p-110;pp-696; shloka600-602
18. Dr. Indra Tripathi;Pandit Narahari; Raja Nighantu Prabhadradi varga/142-143 Choukamba Krishnadas Academy;Varanasi;2003;p-293;pp-704;shloka-142
19. Nrupa Madanapaala; Madanapaala Nighantu Phaladi varga/40-42;Choukamba publications;Varanasi;1998;p-127;pp-271;shloka-40
20. Bhavamishra; Bhavaprakasha Nighantu Amradiphalavarga/67-68;Sri Brahmashankara Mishra; Choukamba Sanskrit Bhavan;11th edition2010;p-568;pp-960; shloka66-68
21. Bapalal G.Vaidya; NighantuadarshaVishatidukadivarga/ p-60-65;pp-841; Chaukhamba Bharati Academy;Varanasi;Vol.2;2009;p-60-65;pp-841
22. Prof. Priyavrit Shama; Priya Nighantu Shatapushpadi varga/197; Choukamba surabharatiprakashan; Varanasi;2004;p-112;pp-275; shloka-197
23. Vaidya Acharya Shodala; Shodala Nighantu Karaveera divarga/394;Dr. Gnyanendra Pandey;ChaukhambaKrishnadas Academy;Varanasi;2009;p-264;pp-538
24. Shaligram Vaidya; Shaligrama Nighantu Phalavarga; Khemarajshri Krishnadas academy;Mumbai;2002;p-452;pp-935
25. Vaidya Banwari Lal Mishra; Dravyagunahastamalaka; Kupeelukula 294 Chaukhamba publications; New delhi;5thedition;2006;p-444;pp-539
26. Kashinath Shastri; Rasa tarangini24/165-166;Motilalbanarasi das;Varanasi;1st edtion;1994; p-676.
27. Kashinath Shastri; Rasa tarangini24/178; Motilalbanarasi das;Varanasi;1st edtion;1994; p-679;pp-772.
28. Vaidya Banwari Lal Mishra; Dravyagunahastamalaka; Chaukhamba publications; New delhi; 4th edition;2004;p-444;pp-528.
29. Ambika data shastri; Bhaishajya Ratnavali 52/13-15;Chaukhambasanskrita samsthana; Varanasi; edition; -20;2010;p-874;pp-1312

30. Ambika data shastri; Bhaishajya Ratnavali 91/15,16; Chaukhambasanskritasamsthana; Varanasi; Edition-20;2010;p-1185;pp-1312
31. Ambika data shastri; Bhaishajya Ratnavali 27/167-169;Chaukhambasanskritasamsthana; Varanasi; edition; -20;2010;p-603;pp-1312
32. Ambika data shastri; Bhaishajya Ratnavali 54/325-327; Chaukhamba sanskritasamsthana;Varanasi; Edition-20;2010;p-911;pp-1312
33. Vaidya Laksmipathishastri; Yoga ratnakarapoorvaardha/ Vaatavyadhinidaana; Choukhamba Sanskrita samsthana;Varanasi;7th edition;2002;poorvaardha; p-531;pp-504
34. Vaidya Laksmipathishastri; Yoga ratnakarapoorvaardha/ Vaatavyadhinidaana ;Choukhamba Sanskrita samsthana;Varanasi;7th edition;2002;poorvaardha; p-531;pp-504
35. Vaidya Laksmipathishastri; Yoga ratnakarauttarardha/ Shwaanavishachikitsa; Choukhamba Sanskrita samsthana;Varanasi;7th edition;2002;uttarardha;p-476;pp-504
36. KashinathShastri; Rasa tarangini24/203;Motilalbanarasi das;Varanasi;edtion;2012;p-684;pp-772
37. KashinathShastri; Rasa tarangini24/210-215;Motilalbanarasidas;Varanasi;edtion;2012;p-685;pp-772
38. Kashinath Shastri; Rasa tarangini 24/216-221 ;Motilalbanarasidas;Varanasi;edtion;2012;p-686;pp-772
39. KashinathShastri; Rasa tarangini 24/222-226 ; Motilalbanarasidas; Varanasi;edtion;2012;p-687;pp-772
40. Kashinath Shastri; Rasa tarangini24/227-229; Motilalbanarasidas; Varanasi;edtion;2012;p-687;pp-772
41. Kashinath Shastri; Rasa tarangini24/230; Motilalbanarasidas; Varanasi;edtion;2012;p-688;pp-772
42. Kashinath Shastri; Rasa tarangini 24/231-233 ; Motilalbanarasidas; Varanasi;edtion;2012;p-688;pp-772
43. Sri Gopal Krishna; Rasendrasarasangraha3/shoolarogachikitsa/53,54; Choukambakrishnadas academy; Varanasi;1st edition;2007;p-688;pp-1112
44. Sri Gopal Krishna; Rasendrasarasangraha3/ shoolarogachikitsa/61-63; Choukambakrishnadas academy; Varanasi;1st edition; 2007;p-692;pp-1112

45. Sri Gopal Krishna; Rasendrasarasangraha3/ shoolarogachikitsa/41-45; Choukambakrishnadas academy; Varanasi;1st edition; 2007;p-628;pp-1112
46. Sri Gopal Krishna; Rasendrasarasangraha3/ shoolarogachikitsa/3-5; Choukambakrishnadas academy; Varanasi;1st edition; 2007;p-840;pp-1112
47. Dr.K.Nishteswar and Dr.R.Vidyanath; Sahasrayogam parishishtaprakarana taila/33; Choukamba Sanskrit series office; Varanasi;2nd edition;2008;p-428;pp-540
48. Dr. Siddhinandan Mishra; Rasaprakashsudhakara 8/85 Chaukhambaorientalia; Varanasi;3rd edition;2004;p-228-230;pp-277
49. Shree Nagindaschaganalalsha; Bharata Bhaishajya Ratnakara; choukhamba publications; newdelhi; vol.-5;edition2012;p316;pp-863
50. Pandit Parashurama;SharangadharasamhitaMa.12/222,223;Choukambaorientalia;Varanasi; 7th edition2008;p-279;pp-398
51. Kashinath Shastri; Rasa tarangini24/172,173;Motilalbanarasi das;Varanasi;11 edtion;1994;p-678
52. Kashinath Shastri; Rasa tarangini24/174,175;Motilalbanarasi das;Varanasi;11 edtion;1994;p-678
53. Kashinath Shastri; Rasa tarangini24/176,177;Motilalbanarasi das;Varanasi;11 edtion;1994;p-679
54. Vishwanath Dwivedi; Bharateeyarasashastra Dwiteeyakhanda; Vihopavisha-7;Sharma Ayurveda mandir;Varanasi;2nd edition2000;p-46;pp-592
55. Vishwanath Dwivedi; Bharateeya rasashastra Dwiteeyakhanda; Vihopavisha-7;Sharma Ayurveda mandir;Varanasi;2nd edition2000;p-46;pp-592
56. Kashinath Shastri; Rasa tarangini24/203;Motilalbanarasi das;Varanasi;1stedtion;1994;p-684.
57. V.M.Kuttikrishna Menon; Kriya Koumudi Sthavaravisha prakaram/853-863;edition 1986;p-760; pp-959.